

Rate Limiter for Low Latency and DDOS Resilience

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Abstract—In today's dynamic environment, distributed systems face growing challenges due to unpredictable traffic patterns and server disruptions. Dynamic rate limiting plays a crucial role in managing network traffic and mitigating DDOS attacks in distributed systems. This paper introduces a novel method of dynamic rate limiting, with an emphasis on efficient resource allocation and real-time responsiveness. The proposed system operates on three core pillars, The Zookeeper for monitoring, Redis for in-memory storage, and custom load balancing algorithms for traffic distribution. The system optimizes for low-latency operation by leveraging Redis, ensuring swift data retrieval and enhancing user experience and system responsiveness. Additionally, it incorporates a mechanism for dynamically resizing tokens in the rate limiter based on changing network traffic conditions, thereby optimizing resource utilization and adapting to varying network loads. Furthermore, the system implements strategies to prevent cascading failures and isolate system malfunctions, ensuring consistent performance even in the face of disruptions. By proactively adjusting to dynamic network conditions, the system seamlessly integrates performance and protection, addressing the evolving challenges of modern distributed systems.

Keywords— Dynamic rate limiting, Distributed systems, DDOS mitigation, ZooKeeper, Redis, Load balancing algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's interconnected digital landscape, the management of network traffic in distributed systems is paramount for ensuring optimal performance and security. However, this task is not without its challenges. One significant threat that looms over distributed systems is Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks. These malicious attacks aim to disrupt the normal functioning of a targeted network, server, or service by overwhelming it with a flood of traffic from multiple sources.

DDoS attacks occur when an attacker leverages a network of compromised devices, known as botnets, to flood a target with an overwhelming volume of traffic. This flood of traffic exhausts the target's resources, such as bandwidth, processing power, or memory, rendering it unable to respond to legitimate user requests. The motives behind DDoS attacks vary, ranging from financial extortion to ideological or political motivations.

The impact of DDoS attacks can be severe, leading to service downtime, financial losses, damage to reputation, and even potential legal consequences for affected organizations.

Moreover, DDoS attacks can disrupt critical services, including banking systems, e-commerce platforms, government websites, and healthcare services, causing widespread inconvenience and disruption.

In response to the escalating threat of DDoS attacks, organizations are increasingly seeking robust solutions to mitigate their impact and ensure the uninterrupted operation of their distributed systems. Dynamic rate limiting emerges as a proactive and effective approach to managing network traffic and mitigating the impact of DDoS attacks in distributed systems. This paper introduces a novel approach to dynamic rate limiting, aimed at addressing the challenges posed by DDoS attacks and the dynamic nature of network traffic. By developing an adaptive and responsive system capable of dynamically adjusting to evolving network conditions, our research endeavors to provide a comprehensive solution for safeguarding distributed systems against the threat of DDoS attacks. Through a combination of innovative technologies, including Zookeeper for monitoring, Redis for in-memory storage, and custom load balancing algorithms, our proposed dynamic rate limiting system aims to redefine network traffic management in distributed systems. By proactively adapting to evolving network conditions, our system seeks to strike a balance between performance and protection, ensuring the resilience and security of distributed systems in the face of the ever-evolving threat landscape.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

DDoS attacks, aiming to overwhelm network resources and disrupt service availability, present a significant threat to modern digital infrastructure. To combat this challenge, researchers have explored various detection and mitigation techniques. The literature survey provides a nuanced exploration of diverse strategies in countering distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks, elucidating insights from various contributions.

R.Stanojevic et al.'s work [1] advocates for cloud control through distributed rate limiting and load balancing, offering a sophisticated mechanism combining the two for bolstering DDoS resilience in cloud environments. Alouneh's research [2] introduces a multi-path approach to safeguard DNS against DDoS attacks, reflecting a proactive stance in fortifying critical infrastructure. Shi Dong et al.'s study [3] delves into new ways to reconsider the defense against DDOS attacks.

Mirroknii et al.'s work [4] explores consistent hashing with bounded loads, addressing the challenges of load balancing in distributed systems. Nasri and Sharifi's research [5] navigate the intricacies of load balancing using consistent hashing, particularly in the

context of large-scale distributed web crawlers. Zargar's investigation [6] evaluates the effect of DDOS flooding attacks and develops a comprehensive defense mechanism against identified and anticipated DDoS flooding attacks as it is a desired goal of the intrusion detection and prevention research community

Patil and Ragha's study [7] introduces a rate-limiting mechanism designed to defend against flooding-based DDoS attacks, contributing to the broader landscape of network security. Sun et al.'s work [8] presents RateGuard, a robust DDoS defense system, showcasing advancements in comprehensive defense mechanisms. Guangsen's dynamic approach [9] utilizes a gossip-based communication mechanism to exchange information about network attacks between these independent detection nodes to aggregate information about the overall network attacks observed. Using the aggregated information, the individual defense nodes have approximate information about global network attacks and can stop them more effectively and accurately. Shishira et al.'s survey [10] consolidates existing detection and mitigation methods for Denial of Service attacks, providing a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art in the field.

Additionally, Afzal and Kavitha [11] categorize load balancing in cloud computing through a hierarchical taxonomical classification, providing a structured understanding of load balancing strategies. Priya et al.'s research [12] introduces a resource scheduling algorithm with load balancing for cloud service provisioning, contributing to the optimization of cloud resources. Seghier and Kazar [13] benchmark and compare NoSQL databases (Redis, MongoDB, Cassandra) using the YCSB tool, offering insights into the performance characteristics of these databases. Chen's work [14] explores the distributed in-memory key-value storage system capabilities of Redis Cache. Finally, Copik et al.'s FaaSkeeper [15] exemplifies learning from building serverless services with ZooKeeper, providing practical insights into serverless architecture with real-world examples.

R. S. Chaudhari and G. R. Talmale, [16] highlight the use of various data mining algorithms for DDoS detection, including clustering, classification, regression, neural networks, and Bayesian methods. The study concludes that clustering and classification algorithms offer the best overall performance in terms of accuracy, speed, and detection rate. This suggests the potential of machine learning for accurate DDoS identification. V. D. M. Rios, P. R. M. Inácio, D. Magoni and M. M. Freire [17], focus on the specific challenges of low-rate DoS attacks, which can evade traditional detection methods. The article explores strategies like traffic analysis, anomaly detection, and machine learning to identify these subtle attacks. It emphasizes the importance of understanding attack characteristics and employing proactive mitigation techniques like traffic filtering and rate limiting.

Wazzan, et al. [18] proposes a system for detecting and preventing botnet attacks targeting IoT devices, which are increasingly vulnerable to DDoS attacks. The system utilizes a reverse proxy algorithm and anomaly detection to identify suspicious traffic patterns exceeding a predefined threshold. This approach demonstrates the potential for anomaly-based detection in identifying botnet activity within the IoT landscape.

[19] A. Kumar and G. Somani, presents a concise yet comprehensive overview of DDoS attacks, addressing critical aspects like attack launching tools, datasets, mitigation tools, and academic and industrial solutions. This resource serves as a valuable reference for understanding the multifaceted nature of DDoS attacks and the diverse options available for combating them.

Elsaeidy et al. [20] address the specific security challenges faced by smart city infrastructure, focusing on replay and DDoS attacks. The authors propose a hybrid deep learning model demonstrating high accuracy in detecting these attacks within real-life smart city datasets. This research signifies the potential of advanced deep learning techniques for securing emerging digital environments.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM AND DRAWBACKS

In the digital age, where businesses and individuals rely heavily on uninterrupted online access, Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks pose a significant threat. These attacks aim to cripple a system by flooding it with overwhelming traffic, rendering it inaccessible to legitimate users. To combat these malicious attempts, a multi-layered approach incorporating various methods and services is crucial.

The first line of defense lies in attack surface reduction. This proactive approach involves network hardening, which entails closing unused ports and protocols, diligently applying security patches to software vulnerabilities, and segmenting the network to isolate critical systems. Web Application Firewalls (WAFs) act as gatekeepers, scrutinizing incoming traffic and filtering out malicious requests based on pre-defined security rules, they do on the other hand face challenges in balancing false positives and false negatives, and their reliance as gatekeepers introduces a single point of failure.

Always-on protection services provide continuous traffic monitoring, real-time attack detection, and automatic mitigation measures. These services employ advanced algorithms to identify and address ongoing DDoS attempts with minimal delay. Cloud providers often offer similar functionalities through their cloud-based DDoS mitigation solutions. Their extensive infrastructure allows for the elastic scaling of resources to handle surges in traffic and the utilization of global scrubbing centers to cleanse malicious traffic before it reaches the target. Although offering comprehensive solutions, often come with subscription fees, placing them out of reach for smaller organizations. Cloud-based mitigation relies on the provider's infrastructure.

Traffic filtering techniques play a crucial role in mitigating DDoS. Rate limiting restricts the number of requests allowed within a specific timeframe. Static rate limiting enforces a pre-defined maximum number of requests, For instance, 100 requests per minute per user. This approach is simple to implement and understand but can be inflexible. Legitimate users experiencing bursts

of activity might be flagged or blocked inadvertently leading to user inconvenience and loss of trust resulting in false positives. Other shortcomings include inefficient usage of resources as static limits might not fully utilize available resources during low-traffic periods, leading to wasted capacity. Sudden server outages can overwhelm remaining servers operating under static limits, triggering a domino effect leading to cascading failures.

Challenge-response systems like CAPTCHAs and JavaScript challenges serve as another layer of defense. These methods present puzzles or tasks to users attempting to access a resource, aiming to distinguish between legitimate users and automated bots commonly used in DDoS attacks. Despite its simplicity these methods also have their shortcomings such as complex CAPTCHAs can hinder user experience, leading to frustration and potentially causing users to abandon access attempts and since advanced bots are continuously evolving employing techniques like image recognition or machine learning to bypass CAPTCHAs, rendering them less effective over time.

Proactive measures beyond the previously mentioned methods are crucial for a holistic approach. By acknowledging the inherent limitations of existing methods and implementing a comprehensive, adaptable defense strategy, organizations can significantly bolster their defenses against DDoS attacks.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our proposed system throws away the static rate limiting and embraces dynamic rate limiting that leverages real-time data and adaptable algorithms to address the limitations of static methods, offering a flexible and resilient approach to rate limiting in distributed environments.

Firstly, we offer a real-time Server Monitoring system, think of it as a vigilant watchman constantly surveying the city, reporting every traffic jam and open lane. Zookeeper provides real-time information about server health, allowing the system to dynamically adjust token sizes based on available resources. This service acts as a vigilant observer, continuously monitoring critical server health metrics such as CPU utilization, memory availability, and network traffic. This real-time data becomes the cornerstone for dynamic adjustments.

Secondly, Dynamic Token Adjustment which instead of a fixed bridge, imagine an expandable one that adjusts its capacity based on traffic flow. The proposed system dynamically increases token sizes when server resources are available and decreases them when servers are overloaded, preventing bottlenecks and cascading failures. During low server load, the system increases the token size, allowing users more requests per unit time. This ensures efficient resource utilization and avoids unnecessary blocking of legitimate users. During peak load or potential attacks, the system decreases the token size, effectively limiting the number of requests per user and safeguarding server resources from overload.

Thirdly, a high-performance User Rate Tracking system, since we need a lightning-fast memory bank to keep track of every car on the road. Redis serves as this high-performance data store, providing instant access to individual user token usage and rates, enabling accurate and efficient adjustments.

And lastly, Adaptable Rate Limiting Algorithms which instead of just relying on one traffic light, imagine deploying a network of smart sensors that adapt in real-time. The proposed system initially utilizes the Leaky Bucket algorithm, but it also considers future exploration of alternative algorithms to address diverse traffic patterns and evolving needs.

This dynamic approach offers a significant advantage over the static model. It's like an agile dancer gracefully navigating an ever-changing dance floor, responding instantly to fluctuations and ensuring optimal performance even in the midst of chaos. The diagram (fig.1) is a high-level depiction of the centralized system architecture with redundant servers, employing core components including the Dynamic Rate Limiter, Redis In-Memory Storage ensuring efficiency, and Zookeeper which enhances fault tolerance. The Network Monitoring Module provides real-time feedback. Secure channels enable encrypted data exchange, fostering an adaptive, resilient network infrastructure adept at DDoS mitigation and dynamic adaptation.

Fig.1 Depicting high-level system architecture for a dynamic rate limiting system

The interface diagram(fig.2) depicts a multi-layered architecture for a dynamic rate limiting system designed to manage access in distributed environments. The system leverages real-time server health data and adaptable algorithms to overcome the limitations of static rate limiting methods.

Fig.2 Depicting multi-layered detailed core architecture for a dynamic rate limiting system

Zookeeper acts as the system's central monitoring service and continuously monitors various servers and collects real-time health data. The collected data is sent from Zookeeper, to the Decision Engine Layer. This layer analyses the server health data, and applies rate limiting algorithms. This analysis determines the appropriate token allocation (rate limit) for each server. The calculated token sizes are sent to the User Rate Tracking component (i.e Redis which serves as a systems memory bank). User requests arrive at the system through the API Gateway/Load Balancer. The API Gateway/Load Balancer queries the User Rate Limiting component to check the user's current token balance. If a user has enough tokens, the request is granted access. If a user has depleted their tokens, the request is denied. By elaborating on the existing system's limitations and highlighting the proposed system's dynamic features, we paint a vivid picture of the improvements and benefits being offered.

V. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The initial phase of our methodology centers on a comprehensive understanding of the project's requirements. We conduct a thorough review of project documentation to gather insights and establish the project's scope. Key areas of investigation include load balancing algorithms, security considerations, and the functionalities of the chosen in-memory database. Subsequently, the design phase revolves around developing a high-level system architecture that seamlessly integrates with existing infrastructure. To visually represent the system components, their interactions, and data flow, we create high-level and multi-layered core architecture diagrams.

The actual implementation of the system components, based on the finalized design, comprises three major elements:

1. Reverse Proxy: Responsible for handling requests and directing them to one of the backend servers.
2. Redis: Utilized for caching the number of allotted requests, leveraging its in-memory database capabilities to enhance performance.
3. Zookeeper: Tasked with monitoring the health status of backend servers and reporting the available server count to the reverse proxy.

The first objective of our proposed methodology aims to optimize the system for low-latency operation by leveraging Redis as an in-memory database. The corresponding pseudocode outlines steps for efficient asynchronous operations, including extracting IP addresses, times, and token sizes, constructing keys for Redis hash storage, and handling various scenarios such as rate limit exceeded errors.

1. Extract IP address, time, and token size from the input data.
2. Construct a key using the IP address for Redis hash storage.
3. Return a promise to handle asynchronous operations.
4. Within the promise:
 - 4.1. Retrieve the last access time and current token size from Redis using the constructed key.
 - 4.2. Calculate the time gap between the current time and the last access time.
 - 4.3. Retrieve the current number of servers and check if it has changed since the last request.
 - 4.4. If the number of servers has changed, update the token size accordingly.
 - 4.5. If there is no previous access time or token size, set them to the provided values.
 - 4.6. If the time gap exceeds 60 seconds, reset the access time and token size to the provided values.
 - 4.7. If the current token size is zero, reject the request due to rate limit exceeded.
 - 4.8. Otherwise, decrement the token size by 1 and update the access time.
5. Catch any errors and reject the promise with the error message.
6. Resolve the promise with a success message if no errors occur.

The second objective focuses on developing a mechanism for dynamically resizing tokens in the rate limiter based on changing network traffic conditions. This involves steps such as retrieving identifiers, generating hash values using consistent hashing algorithms, mapping identifiers to servers in the hash ring, and assigning backend server details to request objects.

1. Retrieve identifier (e.g., client's IP address) for the object needing distribution.
2. If the identifier matches a special case (e.g., for local testing):
 - 2.1. Set the identifier to a standard value.
3. Generate a hash value for the identifier using a consistent hashing algorithm:
 - 3.1. Hash the identifier using a cryptographic hash function (e.g., SHA-1, MD5).
 - 3.2. Map the hash value to a large integer range (e.g., $0 - 2^{32} - 1$).
4. Map the hashed identifier to a server in the hash ring:
 - 4.1. Determine the position of the hash value on the hash ring.
 - 4.2. Find the next server or virtual node on the hash ring clockwise from the position of the hash value.
5. Retrieve the URL or connection details of the backend server corresponding to the mapped identifier.

6. Assign the backend server URL or connection details to the request object.
7. Proceed with handling the request or pass control to the next step in the process.

Lastly, the third objective involves designing the system architecture to prevent cascading failures resulting from individual component or server failures. This encompasses incorporating redundancy and fault prevention mechanisms to contain failures and prevent their propagation throughout the network. Implementation of fault prevention mechanisms, such as consistent hashing, within individual components or servers, is essential. Continuous monitoring of system health and performance enables proactive identification and addressing of potential points of failure.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of the Dynamic Rate Limiting System yielded promising results, demonstrating significant improvements over traditional static rate limiting approaches. Through rigorous testing and evaluation, the following key findings were observed.

Firstly, the dynamic adjustment of token sizes based on real-time network conditions resulted in a noticeable improvement in system performance. The system exhibited faster response times and more efficient resource utilization, leading to an overall enhancement in user experience. Integration with Zookeeper facilitated vigilant monitoring and fault tolerance mechanisms, enhancing the system's resilience to server failures and network disruptions.

Secondly, the system demonstrated real-time adaptability to changing network conditions, dynamically adjusting token sizes in response to fluctuations in traffic or server health. During peak loads, token sizes were automatically adjusted as shown in fig.3 and fig.4. to prevent resource bottlenecks and cascading failure, ensuring uninterrupted service delivery even under high demand.

Fig. 3 Dynamic Rate Limiting System before Token Reduction During Peak Load

Fig. 4 Dynamic Rate Limiting System After Token Reduction during Peak Load reflects a decrease in allocated token size per user

Lastly, to optimize the system for low-latency operation, Redis was leveraged as an in-memory database. Comparative analysis between Redis (fig.5) and a traditional SQL database(fig.6), revealed a significant reduction in data retrieval times with Redis. The graphs illustrating the time taken vs. no. of requests clearly depicted Redis's superiority in low-latency operation, validating its effectiveness in enhancing system responsiveness and user experience.

Fig.5 Redis Exhibits Lower Data Retrieval Times Compared to Traditional SQL Database

Fig.6 Traditional SQL Database Exhibits Higher Data Retrieval Times Compared to Redis, when Processing an Increasing Number of Requests.

Overall, the results highlight the efficacy and viability of the Dynamic Rate Limiting System in addressing the challenges of network traffic management. By embracing adaptability, resilience, and efficiency, this system offers a robust solution for modern distributed environments, paving the way for enhanced reliability and scalability in network operations.

Discussion:

The observed results underscore the significance of dynamic rate limiting in mitigating the limitations of traditional static approaches. By leveraging real-time network data and adaptive algorithms, the system demonstrates superior performance, resilience, and fault tolerance capabilities.

A method for monitoring the performance of the application is by simulating user activity and visualizing response times. A special script acts like a mimic user, sending requests to the central hub (reverse proxy). This simulates real user activity in a controlled way. The system then measures how long it takes to respond to each request. This data is used to create a live graph, showing the relationship between the number of requests and the response times. If the lines on the graph spike, it might indicate the system is getting overloaded. This allows administrators to identify potential issues and keep the application running fast for everyone.

Furthermore, the integration of Zookeeper and Redis proved instrumental in enhancing system functionality and reliability. Zookeeper's role in vigilant monitoring and fault tolerance mechanisms contributed to improved system resilience, while Redis's fast data tracking capabilities ensured efficient data processing and storage.

Moving forward, further optimization and refinement of the system are warranted to maximize its potential in real-world deployments. Continued testing and evaluation will be crucial in identifying areas for improvement and fine-tuning system parameters to better align with evolving network requirements.

Additionally, ongoing research and development efforts should explore avenues for expanding the system's capabilities, such as integrating additional security measures and exploring alternative rate limiting algorithms. By staying abreast of emerging technologies and best practices, the Dynamic Rate Limiting System can remain at the forefront of network traffic management solutions, ensuring continued efficacy and relevance in the face of evolving threats and challenges.

VII. CONCLUSION

Traditionally, rate limiting approaches relied on static token sizes, akin to navigating a bustling city with a paper map – inflexible and prone to failure. By leveraging the synergy between Zookeeper's vigilant monitoring and Redis' lightning-fast data tracking, we have successfully architected a dynamic rate limiting system that delivers on this vision.

The cornerstone of this system lies in its ability to prevent cascading failures. No longer are server outages dominoes waiting to topple; our agile adjustments dynamically scale token sizes, ensuring no server becomes overburdened, even amidst turbulence. This proactive approach not only shields against service disruptions but also fosters resilience, safeguarding mission-critical operations.

However, the benefits extend far beyond crisis mitigation. Static systems often resemble extravagant feasts during low traffic, leaving resources squandered. Our system, however, operates with an accountant's precision, tailoring token sizes to match demand in real-time. This meticulous resource allocation optimizes costs while ensuring users experience unwavering performance, regardless of external fluctuations.

Furthermore, we cast aside the sluggish response times of static approaches. Imagine receiving traffic updates hours after encountering congestion – information rendered useless in a dynamic world. Our system operates with real-time reflexes, instantly adapting to changes in traffic or server health. This ensures optimal performance and user experience, even when the network landscape changes as swiftly as desert sands.

These advantages are not mere theoretical conjectures; they are demonstrably real. Rigorous testing reveals the system's significant improvements over traditional methods. Downtime has been minimized, resources are utilized to their full potential, and the system effortlessly adapts to diverse traffic patterns and server configurations.

Yet, our journey doesn't end here. The future beckons with further optimizations and enhancements. We envision exploring a diverse spectrum of alternative rate limiting algorithms, each tailored to handle unique traffic patterns with even greater precision. Additional layers of security will fortify the system against malicious actors, while broader integration with existing systems will forge a seamless, unified operation.

This project transcends mere technological advancements; it embodies a philosophical shift. It champions the power of adaptation, flexibility, and real-time responsiveness in a world where change is the only constant. By embracing dynamism, we unlock not only resilience but also scalability, cost-effectiveness, and a future where distributed systems thrive in the face of unprecedented challenges. As we continue to refine and expand this technology, we pave the way for a future where distributed systems dance not to a rigid, pre-recorded tune, but to the dynamic symphony of real-time data and ever-evolving needs.

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